

Numerical solution of fractional partial differential equations using fractional-order Lagrange polynomials

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Abstract. In this paper, we present the numerical method for solving fractional partial differential equations using the fractional-order Lagrange polynomials (FLPs). A new operational matrix of Caputo fractional derivative of FLPs is driven. Using this matrix and collocation method the problem can be reduced to a set of algebraic equations. The method is tested on examples. The results show that the FLPs yields better results.

Keywords: Fractional-order Lagrange polynomials; Fractional partial differential equations; Operational matrix

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1 Introduction

Fractional order partial differential equations, as generalizations of classical integer order partial differential equations, are increasingly used to model problems in flow, finance and other areas of application. Therefore, it is important to develop efficient and fast convergent method to solve fractional partial differential. Recently, many numerical methods have been proposed. For instance, generalized fractional-order Legendre functions [1], Wavelet method [2].

In the next section, we describe some necessary definitions required for our subsequent development. In Section 3, we recall fractional-order Lagrange polynomials and we obtain a new FLPs operational matrix of fractional order derivative for the solution of PDEs. In Section 4, the proposed method is presented. In Some numerical examples to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method are given in the Section 5. Our conclusion is given in Section 6.

2 Preliminaries and notations

Definition 1. Caputo fractional derivative of order ν is defined as [3]

$$D^\nu f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\nu)} \int_0^x \frac{f^{(m)}(\tau)}{(x-\tau)^{\nu-m+1}} d\tau, \quad (1)$$

for $m-1 < \nu \leq m$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $t > 0$. For the Caputo derivative we have:

$$D^\nu x^k = \begin{cases} 0, & \nu \in \mathbb{N}_0, k < \nu, \\ \frac{k!}{\Gamma(k-\nu+1)} x^{k-\nu}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Fractional-order Lagrange functions

The analytic form of fractional-order Lagrange functions $L_i^\alpha(x)$ is as follows [3]

$$L_i^\alpha(x) = \sum_{s=0}^n \beta_{is} x^{\alpha(n-s)}, \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (3)$$

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where $\beta_{i0} = \frac{1}{\prod_{\substack{j=0 \\ i \neq j}}^n (x_i - x_j)}$,

$$\beta_{is} = \frac{(-1)^s}{\prod_{\substack{j=0 \\ i \neq j}}^n (x_i - x_j)} \sum_{k_s=k_{s-1}+1}^n \cdots \sum_{k_1=0}^{n-s+1} \prod_{r=1}^s x_{k_r}, \quad s = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad i \neq k_1 \neq \dots \neq k_s.$$

In this study, we choose the points of Lagrange polynomials $x_i = \frac{i}{n}$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, n$.

3 Function approximation

Let $H = L^2[0, 1]$ and suppose that $\{L_0^\alpha(x), L_1^\alpha(x), \dots, L_n^\alpha(x)\} \subset H$ is the set of Lagrange polynomials and $Y = span\{L_0^\alpha(x), L_1^\alpha(x), \dots, L_n^\alpha(x)\}$, and assume that y is an arbitrary element in H . Y is a finite dimension vector space, then y has the unique best approximation out of Y such as $y_n \in Y$, that is $\|y - y_n\| \leq \|y - f\|, \forall f \in Y$. $y_n \in Y$, then there exist unique coefficients c_0, c_1, \dots, c_n such that

$$y(x) \simeq y_n(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n c_i L_i^\alpha(x) = C^T L^\alpha(x), \tag{4}$$

where $C = [c_0, c_1, \dots, c_n]^T$, $L(x) = [L_0^\alpha(x), L_1^\alpha(x), \dots, L_n^\alpha(x)]^T$. Using Eq. (4), we obtain $y_j = \langle y, L_j^\alpha \rangle$, where $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ denotes inner product, therefore

$$y_j \simeq \sum_{i=0}^n c_i \int_0^1 L_i^\alpha(x) L_j^\alpha(x) x^{\alpha-1} dx = \sum_{i=0}^n c_i d_{ij}, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, n,$$

that $d_{ij} = \int_0^1 L_i^\alpha(x) L_j^\alpha(x) x^{\alpha-1} dx$, $i, j = 0, 1, \dots, n$ and $D = [d_{ij}]$. So, we have $\tilde{Y} = D^T C$, $\tilde{Y} = [y_0, y_1, \dots, y_n]^T$, then we can obtain vector of C uniquely.

4 The FLPs operational matrix of fractional-order derivative

The derivative of the function vector L^α can be approximated as follows

$$D^\nu L^\alpha(x) \simeq D^{(\nu, \alpha)} L^\alpha(x),$$

$D^{(\nu, \alpha)}$ is called the FLPs operational matrix of derivative in the Caputo sense. Using Eqs. (4) and (2), we have

$$D^\nu L_i(x) = D^\nu \left(\sum_{s=0}^n \beta_{is} x^{\alpha(n-s)} \right) = \sum_{s=0}^n \beta_{is} D^\nu x^{\alpha(n-s)} = \sum_{s=0}^n w_{i,s} x^{\alpha(n-s)-\nu}, \tag{5}$$

where $w_{i,s} = \frac{\Gamma(\alpha(n-s)+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha(n-s)+1-\nu)} \beta_{i,s}$. Now, we can expand $x^{\alpha(n-s)-\nu}$ in terms of FLPs as:

$$x^{\alpha(n-s)-\nu} = \sum_{j=0}^n c_{s,j} L_j^\alpha(x), \tag{6}$$

with $c_{s,j} = \frac{\langle x^{\alpha(n-s)-\nu}, L_j^\alpha(x) \rangle}{\langle L_j^\alpha(x), L_j^\alpha(x) \rangle}$ and substitute in Eq.(5), we get

$$D^\nu L_i^\alpha(x) \simeq \sum_{s=0}^n w_{i,s} \sum_{j=0}^n c_{s,j} L_j^\alpha(x) = \sum_{j=0}^n \left(\sum_{s=0}^n w_{i,s} c_{s,j} \right) L_j^\alpha(x) = \sum_{j=0}^n \sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{i,j,s}^\alpha L_j^\alpha(x), \tag{7}$$

where $\theta_{i,j,s}^\alpha = w_{i,s} c_{s,j}$.

We obtain $D^\nu L_i^\alpha(x) \simeq \left[\sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{i,0,s}^\alpha, \sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{i,1,s}^\alpha, \dots, \sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{i,n,s}^\alpha \right] L^\alpha(x)$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, n$.

Therefore, we have

$$D^{(\nu,\alpha)} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{0,0,s}^\alpha & \sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{0,1,s}^\alpha & \cdots & \sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{0,n,s}^\alpha \\ \sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{1,0,s}^\alpha & \sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{1,1,s}^\alpha & \cdots & \sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{1,n,s}^\alpha \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{n,0,s}^\alpha & \sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{n,1,s}^\alpha & \cdots & \sum_{s=0}^n \theta_{n,n,s}^\alpha \end{bmatrix}.$$

5 Numerical method

We consider a class of fractional partial differential equations with variable coefficients as follows:

$$a(x) \frac{\partial^\nu u(x,t)}{\partial x^\nu} + b(t) \frac{\partial^\gamma u(x,t)}{\partial t^\gamma} + c(x) \frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} + d(x)u(x,t) = g(x,t), \tag{8}$$

with the initial condition $u(x,0) = \mu(x)$, and the boundary conditions $u(0,t) = \eta_0(t), u(1,t) = \eta_1(t)$, where $0 \leq x \leq 1, 0 \leq t \leq 1$ and $0 < \nu, \gamma \leq 1$.

Here the fractional derivative is defined as the Caputo fractional derivative. The continuous functions $g(x,t), a(x), b(t), c(x)$ and $d(x)$ are known, the function $u(x,t)$ is unknown.

If we approximate the unknown function $u(x,t)$ by terms of the FLPs, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x,t) &\approx (L^\alpha(x))^T UL^\beta(t), & g(x,t) &\approx (L^\alpha(x))^T GL^\beta(t), \\ a(x) &\approx A^T L^\alpha(x), & b(t) &\approx B^T L^\beta(t), & c(x) &\approx C^T L^\alpha(x), & d(x) &\approx \tilde{d}^T L^\alpha(x), \\ \frac{\partial^\nu u(x,t)}{\partial x^\nu} &\approx (L^\alpha(x))^T (D^{(\nu,\alpha)})^T UL^\beta(t), & \frac{\partial^\gamma u(x,t)}{\partial t^\gamma} &\approx (L^\alpha(x))^T UD^{(\gamma,\beta)} L^\beta(t) \\ \frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2} &\approx (L^\alpha(x))^T (D^{(2,\alpha)})^T UL^\beta(t). \end{aligned}$$

where $G = \{g_{ij}\}_{i,j=0}^{m,n}$, $A^T = \{a_i\}_{i=0}^n$, $B^T = \{b_j\}_{j=0}^m$, $C^T = \{c_i\}_{i=0}^n$, $\tilde{d}^T = \{d_i\}_{i=0}^n$. Using above equations, we rewrite Eq. (8),

$$\begin{aligned} A^T L^\alpha(x) (L^\alpha(x))^T (D^{(\nu,\alpha)})^T UL^\beta(t) &+ B^T L^\beta(t) (L^\beta(t))^T (D^{(\gamma,\beta)})^T U^T L^\alpha(x) \\ &+ C^T L^\alpha(x) (L^\alpha(x))^T (D^{(2,\alpha)})^T UL^\beta(t) \\ &+ \tilde{d}^T L^\alpha(x) (L^\alpha(x))^T UL^\beta(t) \\ &- (L^\alpha(x))^T GL^\beta(t) = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Also, for the initial and boundary conditions, we have

$$(L^\alpha(x))^T UL^\beta(0) - \mu(x) = 0, \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, \tag{10}$$

$$(L^\alpha(0))^T UL^\beta(t) - \eta_0(t) = 0, \tag{11}$$

$$(L^\alpha(1))^T UL^\beta(1) - \eta_1(t) = 0, \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1. \tag{12}$$

We collocate Eqs. (9)-(12) at nodes of Lagrange polynomials. The number of the unknown coefficients u_{ij} is $(n+1)(m+1)$ and can be obtained from these Eqs. Consequently $u(x,t)$ given in Eq. (8) can be calculated.

6 Numerical examples

Example 1: We consider the following equation [4]

$$\frac{\partial^\nu u(x, t)}{\partial x^\nu} + \frac{\partial^\gamma u(x, t)}{\partial t^\gamma} = g(x, t), \quad u(0, t) = 0. \tag{13}$$

The exact solution of this problem is $u(x, t) = x^{1/2}t$, where $\nu = \gamma = 1/2$, $g(x, t) = \sqrt{\pi}t/2 + 2\sqrt{tx}/\sqrt{\pi}$.

Using method proposed in Section 5, for $m = n = 2$, $\alpha = \beta = 1/2$, we obtain numerical solution that the maximum error for this method is 4.39709×10^{-16} , however this error for Haar wavelet ($m=64$) [2] is 1.678×10^{-2} and for method based on Sinc-Legendre ($m=25$) [5] is 6.462×10^{-5} .

Example 2: Consider the following equation

$$a(x)\frac{\partial^\nu u(x, t)}{\partial x^\nu} + b(t)\frac{\partial^\gamma u(x, t)}{\partial t^\gamma} = g(x, t), \quad u(0, t) = u(x, 0) = 0, \quad (x, t) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \tag{14}$$

where $\nu = \gamma = 1/2$, $a(x) = x$, $b(t) = 1$, $g(x, t) = \frac{2t^{1/2}x}{\sqrt{\pi}} + \frac{2tx^{3/2}}{\sqrt{\pi}}$.

The exact solution of this problem is $u(x, t) = xt$. We apply our method for this problem in $n = 3$, $m = 2$. The absolute error for different values of α, β is shown in Table 1.

Tab. 1: The absolute error of $n = 3$, $m = 2$ and different α, β for Example. 2

x	$\alpha = \beta = 1$			$\alpha = \beta = 1/2$		
	$t = 0.2$	$t = 0.4$	$t = 0.8$	$t = 0.2$	$t = 0.4$	$t = 0.8$
0.1	2.50587×10^{-4}	5.53963×10^{-4}	1.31908×10^{-3}	2.52467×10^{-15}	2.52107×10^{-15}	1.46784×10^{-15}
0.3	2.79660×10^{-4}	6.34393×10^{-4}	1.56908×10^{-3}	7.54914×10^{-16}	8.40963×10^{-16}	7.19003×10^{-16}
0.5	2.03924×10^{-5}	7.75043×10^{-5}	3.01887×10^{-4}	4.89887×10^{-16}	3.56764×10^{-16}	1.42755×10^{-16}
0.7	1.17865×10^{-4}	2.37495×10^{-4}	4.82051×10^{-4}	7.43045×10^{-16}	6.06981×10^{-16}	7.26139×10^{-18}
0.9	2.74239×10^{-4}	5.68603×10^{-4}	1.21770×10^{-3}	1.79090×10^{-17}	1.16205×10^{-16}	3.36503×10^{-16}

7 Concluding remarks

In this paper, we present a new FLP operational matrix of fractional derivative. This matrix together with collocation method are used to simplify and effectively calculate the numerical solution of fractional partial differential equations. By some numerical examples, we analysed the accuracy and validity of the presented method through numerical simulations. We believe that the present method can be extended to solve the system of fractional partial differential equations.

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